

ISic0490

I.Sicily inscription 0490

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucio) Acilio L(uci) f(ilio)

2. Rufo I[Iviro]

3. co[] ter[---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

co[lonia] T(h)er[mitanorum], Mommsen (after Huelsen)

Translation (en)

(Set up for) Lucius Acilius Rufus, son of Lucius, duumvir [...]

Commentary

Quite possibly erected by the colonia Thermitanorum. A man of the same name is named as quaestor Siciliae in CIL 10.7344 = ILTermini no.8 = ILPalermo no.53 = ISic0052 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0052>]

Digital identifiers:

TM 491716

EDCS 22000796

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7210 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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